

Data management plan for "Advancing MAS NMR as a Tool for Investigation of Mechanochemical Fluorination Reactions" project.

Version 1

Description

The data management plan outlines the strategy for managing, storing and sharing the data generated in the Advancing MAS NMR as a Tool for Investigation of Mechanochemical Fluorination Reactions project. The plan involves storage of NMR data, computational data and other types of relevant data such as X-ray crystallography data.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Advancing MAS NMR as a Tool for Investigation of Mechanochemical Fluorination Reactions

Researchers

Martins Balodis (0009-0007-8775-0216)

Organizations

Latvijas Organiskās Sintēzes Institūts

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Data management plan for "Advancing MAS NMR as a Tool for Investigation of Mechanochemical Fluorination Reactions" project.

Description:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grants: Advancing MAS NMR as a Tool for Investigation of Mechanochemical Fluorination Reactions

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2025-12-31

4. Templates

Descriptions

Solid state NMR Data for "Advancing MAS NMR as a Tool for Investigation of Mechanochemical Fluorination Reaction" project

This dataset contains solid state NMR data for studying mechanochemical reactions as part of the project.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The data is a collection of solid state NMR data on the mechanochemical reactions in the project.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

Others

JCAMP-DX and in the original Topspin format

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

2

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

I have, but the solid state NMR data is sparse and no relevant data is available.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

To other solid state NMR spectroscopists studying mechanochemical reactions or the same reactants/products as in this work.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until the end of the project.

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

There is no one common solid state NMR database.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

JDXview, Topspin or MestreNova as few alternatives to view the data.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Yes

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

JCAMP-DX format is open and usable either by already established software or openable using self written codes.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2027-04-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

Project budget allocation.

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Martins Balodis (0009-0007-8775-0216)

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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